

ARALASH TENGLAMA UCHUN INTEGRAL ULASH SHARTLI CHEGARAVIY MASALA

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Ushbu ishda Riman-Liuuill kasr tartibli hosila ishtrok etgan aralash tenglama uchun aralash sohada Volterra integral operatorli ulash shartli chegaraviy masalaning yagona yechimi mavjudligi tadqiq qilinadi.

$$f(x, y) = \begin{cases} U_{xx}(x, y) - D_{0y}^{\alpha} U(x, y), & (x, y) \in \Omega_0 \\ U_{xx}(x, y) - U_{yy}(x, y), & (x, y) \in \Omega_i \quad (i=1, 2) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

tenglamani $\Omega = \Omega_0 \cup \Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2 \cup AA_0 \cup BB_0$ aralash sohada tadqiq qilamiz.

Bu yerda $f(x, y)$ -berilgan funksiya, $D_{0y}^{\alpha} U$ esa α kasr tartibli Riman-Liuuill integro-differsial operatori bo'lib, u $0 < \alpha < 1$ uchun quydagicha aniqlangan [1]:

$$D_{0y}^{\alpha} g(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dt} \int_0^t (t-z)^{-\alpha} g(z) dz.$$

(1) tenglama uchun Ω sohada

1-rasm

quyidagi masalani tadqiq etamiz:

1-Masala. (1) tenglamaning Ω sohada

$$U(x, y) \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \cap AC^1(\Omega_0) \cap C^2(\Omega_i), \quad U_{xx} \in C(\Omega_0)$$

funksiyalar sinfiga tegishli quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantiradigan regulyar yechimi topilsin:

$$U(x, 0) = 0, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1,$$

$$U|_{A_0C} = \varphi(y), \quad \frac{1}{2} \leq y \leq 1,$$

$$U|_{B_0D} = \psi(y), \quad \frac{1}{2} \leq y \leq 1,$$

$$U_x(0+, y) = I_1(U(x, y)|_{x=0-}), \quad U_y(0+, y) = U_y(0-, y), \quad 0 < y < 1,$$

$$U_x(1-0, y) = I_2(U_x(x, y)|_{x=1+0}), \quad U_y(1-0, y) = U_y(1+0, y), \quad 0 < y < 1.$$

Bu yerda $\varphi(y)$, $\psi(y)$ -berilgan funksiyalar, I_1, I_2 lar esa hozircha ixtiyoriy integral operatorlar. Bunday tipdagi masalalar I_1 va I_2 integral operatorlarning

maxsus ko‘rinishida [2] da ($\alpha = 1$ holda) hamda $0 < \alpha < 1$ uchun [3] tadqiq etilgan.

Tenglama parabolik tipga tegishli bo‘lgan sohada 2-chegaraviy masala, giperbolik tipga tegishli bo‘lgan sohalarda Koshi masalasi yechimidan foydalanib, tadqiq etilgan masala ekvivalent tarzida Volterra integral tenglamalar sistemasiga keltirilgan.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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